

1 Planning the Safeguarding of Cultural 2 Property in Archaeological Museums. 3 The case of the Musée d'Archéologie 4 Nationale (National Archaeological 5 Museum)

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15 **ABSTRACT**

16 This paper presents a case study conducted at the Musée d'Archéologie Nationale
17 (National Archaeology Museum) in Saint-Germain-en-Laye, France, to initiate the
18 implementation of a Disaster Risk Management (DRM) strategy as part of the
19 museum's wider safeguarding plan to protect its archaeological collections from
20 potential risks. It responds to calls from both national and international cultural
21 organisations to implement DRM strategies within cultural heritage institutions,
22 emphasising the importance of preparedness in an era marked by increasing in
23 frequency and intensity of natural and anthropogenic disasters worldwide.

24 This study draws on guidelines published by international cultural organisations to
25 implement the first stage of the DRM cycle, to assess, mitigate, and prepare for
26 potential risks. Having identified fire as the primary risk capable of causing irreversible
27 damage to the museum's collections, an evacuation-based approach is determined to
28 be the optimal solution to safeguard collections, through which the study then
29 proposes and develops a database application to ensure effective and efficient
30 emergency evacuations when needed.

31 The resulting database has been adopted as the foundation of the museum's DRM
32 strategy and provides a valuable reference for cultural institutions housing moveable
33 heritage. In summary, this study offers a blueprint for mitigating and countering risks
34 to protect invaluable heritage for the future.

35
36 **Keywords:** Risk Mitigation, Heritage Conservation, Museology, Digitisation, Cultural
37 Management

38 **Introduction**

39 Over the past decade, disasters worldwide have made headlines for destroying significant
40 portions of cultural institutions housing moveable heritage. Examples include the 2021 European
41 floods, which extensively damaged archaeological repositories in the Benelux countries (De Bruyn
42 & Olbrechts, 2025), and the 2018 fire at the National Museum of Brazil that destroyed nearly 90
43 per cent of its collections (Wegener, 2024). Despite the widespread belief that disasters are events

44 beyond human control, against which little can be done, it is often overlooked that precautionary
45 measures can significantly reduce the risks they pose.

46 As highlighted by international cultural organisations, damage from potential risks can be
47 minimised and mitigated if Disaster Risk Management (DRM) planning is adequately implemented
48 prior to disasters (UNESCO, 2010). However, research by various scholars and organisations has
49 shown that many heritage sites worldwide continue to lack adequate DRM, either due to the lack
50 of budget, personnel, space, or knowledge in this crucial field (Durrant et al., 2023; RE-ORG,
51 2011).

52 Institutions housing archaeological or heritage collections are particularly vulnerable, as these
53 objects are often fragile and sensitive. In the European context, the situation is especially dire for
54 museums. Both national and international surveys showed that only a minority of museums have
55 conducted risk assessments, and even fewer have a functioning DRM strategy in place
56 (Desplanches & Charline, 2020; NEMO, 2022; Tomastik et al., 2020; Tosun & Bosan, 2022). This
57 highlights the urgent need to develop and implement effective safeguarding measures and
58 emergency preparedness plans to respond to potential disasters.

59 **The Case Study**

60 The Musée d'Archéologie Nationale (National Archaeology Museum, hereafter MAN) is
61 France's preeminent archaeological museum due to the scale and significance of its collections.
62 Located about 20 kilometres west of Paris, the MAN houses one of the largest archaeological
63 collections in Europe, comprising around three million archaeological objects dating from the
64 Palaeolithic era to the Early Middle Ages (MAN, 2023). Objects are predominantly from
65 excavations within the French territory, although smaller collections from other cultures are also
66 presented. The MAN is situated within a former royal castle complex known as the Château de
67 Saint-Germain-en-Laye, a national monument that once served as a former royal residence for
68 French kings, before being converted into a museum in 1862 (MAN, 2017).

69 One of the main reasons the MAN lacked a functioning DRM plan prior to this study lies in the
70 constraints imposed by its location. The castle structure cannot be altered due to its status as a
71 historic monument, and combined with the sheer volume of objects under its care, this makes the
72 movement and management of collections particularly challenging, thereby limiting large-scale
73 research (MAN, 2017, 2023). Moreover, the department of collections management responsible
74 for overseeing the conservation of objects was only established in 2017, with much of its efforts
75 focused on the digital documentation of the many collections that had yet to be recorded (MAN,
76 2023). For these reasons, although small scale preliminary risk assessments have been made
77 previously, a more comprehensive DRM strategy has yet to be extensively researched, which put
78 the museum's collections at risk of disasters.

79 Consequently, to safeguard the many invaluable moveable heritage housed within one of
80 France's most important museums, this study addresses the following questions: What is the
81 primary risk that threatens the MAN? How should the MAN mitigate from the said risk? What are
82 the tools and strategies to safeguard the museum's archaeological collections?

83 **Related Work**

84 Various international organisations have long advocated for DRM planning in cultural heritage
85 sites. They have published detailed guidelines over the past decade, tailored to different types of
86 heritage contexts, to enable both museum and heritage professionals to gain a holistic
87 understanding of the safeguarding actions that needs to be taken (ICCROM, 2016; ICCROM &
88 UNESCO, 2016; ICOM, 2017).

89 In fact, case studies have been performed in selected cultural institutions, particularly those
90 situated in areas prone to natural disasters, illustrating the necessity of implementing DRM plans.
91 For instance, case studies conducted at various museums and institutions housing movable
92 heritage have highlighted the effectiveness of thorough risk assessment and mitigation, as well as
93 the need for greater general awareness to hasten DRM implementation (Bülbül Bahtiyar & Dişli,

94 2022; Najar & Wani, 2021; Rodríguez-Rosales et al., 2021). These studies derived their
95 methodology from the guidelines recommended by cultural organisations, thereby demonstrating
96 the effectiveness of the guidelines in practice.

97 Furthermore, in the aftermath of disaster scenarios for heritage institutions that suffered
98 extensive damage, such as those mentioned earlier in introduction, evaluation reports by
99 researchers and government agencies concluded that adequate risk assessment and mitigation
100 planning performed prior to the disasters would have minimised the damage inflicted on the
101 collections (Da Rocha et al., 2025; De Bruyn & Olbrechts, 2025). These findings echo the broader
102 consensus within the field that the implementation of proactive DRM measures is essential, and
103 that the integration of comprehensive DRM planning into institutional practices is necessary to
104 effectively safeguard cultural heritage from risks (UNESCO, 2015).

105 **Definition and Methodology**

106 International organisations have established definitions and guidelines, based on expert
107 recommendations, that outline best practices for heritage risk management. A disaster is defined
108 as “a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society causing widespread human,
109 material, economic or environmental losses” (UNESCO, 2010, p.58), while risk is defined as “the
110 chance of something happening that will have a negative impact” (ICCROM, 2016, p.9). In this
111 context, disaster risk refers to the possibility that such disruptions may result in losses to heritage.
112 Disaster Risk Management is therefore the process of planning, implementing, evaluating
113 strategies with the aim of reducing disaster risks and strengthening resilience (UNESCO, 2010).

114 DRM comprises three main phases: before, during, and after disasters (UNESCO, 2010).
115 Before disasters, preparations are made in that risks are identified and assessed, so institutions
116 can mitigate or prevent risks, and establish response plans. During disasters, the prepared
117 response plans are activated to minimise damage. After disasters, the effectiveness of response
118 plans and damage are assessed to prevent future disasters. The preparedness phase before
119 disasters is therefore the most critical for limiting potential damage.

120 Thus, this study is geared towards establishing the foundations for the preparedness phase for
121 the MAN, as the museum has not developed a full DRM strategy. Structured in accordance with
122 international guidelines, the research adopts a mixed-methods approach. Primary data were
123 collected between June 2022 and May 2023 through field research and iterative group discussions
124 with relevant parties to the MAN’s DRM. Secondary data, including government and institutional
125 reports on local environmental and human factors, and existing reports by the MAN were
126 synthesised to support the development of the safeguard framework.

127 **Results**

128 **Risk Assessment at the MAN**

129 There are ten distinct categories of natural and human-induced risks that threaten moveable
130 heritage (ICCROM, 2016). This section summarises the preliminary assessments performed
131 previously at the MAN, combined with personal field research conducted in 2022, to establish the
132 baseline for this study. As scientific reports have already catalogued certain vulnerabilities within
133 the museum (MAN, 2017), this study does not aim to conduct an exhaustive primary risk analysis.
134 Instead, these prior findings are summarised and integrated with current field observations to
135 validate the existing threat landscape. This synthesis serves as a prerequisite to the next stage of
136 the DRM, to develop a targeted mitigation strategy that the MAN currently lacks. The following
137 texts summarises the findings for each of the ten risk categories.

138 *Criminals*

139 The threat of criminal acts against a national museum cannot be ruled out, for sites of cultural
140 significance and importance have often been used as places to carry out an attack or targets for
141 theft (EUROPOL, 2022). However, the museum is actively implementing recommendations to

142 reduce criminal risks from a comprehensive audit performed in 2013, thereby decreasing the
143 likelihood of criminal acts (MAN, 2017).

144 *Dissociation*

145 There are objects which are yet to be documented digitally, as observed during the field
146 research. The museum is housed within a castle that was not originally designed for museum use,
147 and so its interior layout makes it difficult to access and document the many objects in storage,
148 particularly due to the lack of adequate space for scientific research. The MAN has nonetheless
149 partially closed sections of the museum since 2020, to make room for temporary on-site research
150 facility, and is actively digitally documenting the remaining objects to resolve this.

151 *Fire*

152 The possibility of fire can start both externally and internally. Externally, leaks or explosions of
153 combustible gases from the nearby Seveso establishments, or fires from drought, lighting strikes,
154 or human factors to a nearby forest could potentially make the castle catch fire (Institut Paris
155 Région, 2015). Internally, the museum is currently undergoing major renovations aimed to
156 refurbish and reorganise the museum's interior spaces (MAN, 2023). Coupled with the fact that
157 much of the interior structure is made of non-fireproof materials such as wood, fires can also be
158 started accidentally from construction, electrical short circuit, or other human factors such as
159 unextinguished cigarettes.

160 *Incorrect RH (relative humidity)*

161 Through the creation of the collections department in 2017, the RH has been consistently
162 monitored using calibrated equipment and showcases with objects sensitive to RH are regulated
163 to maintain the integrity of objects (MAN, 2023).

164 *Incorrect temperature*

165 As observed during field research, the MAN possesses both heating and air ventilation systems
166 that prevents extreme temperature fluctuations within the castle compound. Regular reviews of the
167 thermostats ensure the optimal condition for the museum's objects.

168 *Light and UV*

169 The windows of all rooms within the castle are noted to have blinds or filters, or are covered up
170 completely, which prevents strong UV from damaging the artefacts. Individual showcases also
171 have ultraviolet and infrared filters that prevents excessive radiation damage (MAN, 2023).

172 *Pollutants*

173 The museum's air circulation is sealed from the outside, as windows are noted to be rarely
174 opened. The object showcases also provide limited air circulation, which prevents exterior
175 pollutants from entering.

176 *Pests*

177 On occasion during field research, flies and other common insects have been found to have
178 entered the museum. Nonetheless, pesticides are seen throughout the compound to eliminate the
179 possibility of pests damaging the objects. The more vulnerable objects are also encased.

180 *Water*

181 The area in which the castle is located is not prone to flooding, as the castle sits on a plateau
182 120 metres higher than the average levels of the Seine River that flows nearby (Préfet des
183 Yvelines, 2020). The ageing pipelines are a point of concern due to occasional leakages, so the
184 current renovations include upgrades to the water systems (MAN, 2023).

185 Taking all the potential risks into account, it is determined that fire poses the most imminent
186 threat to the museum's collections. This is due to the growing concern that fire is a risk that can
187 start from not only the outside but also within the museum, with chances especially heightened

188 under the currently ongoing major renovations. The inability to protect objects from fire on-site, due
189 to the current museum conditions of the primarily wooden interior and the vulnerability of most of
190 the objects, necessitates an immediate approach to mitigate the risk.

191 **Risk Mitigation at the MAN**

192 The following procedure, according to the DRM cycle, would be to mitigate from the
193 aforementioned risk (UNESCO, 2010). However, as the museum is housed inside a historical
194 monument, certain safety requirements cannot be applied to the MAN. For example, an automatic
195 fire sprinkler system cannot be installed to protect the collections, as excessive water could
196 damage the castle's interior structural integrity, as well as the showcases, which are not always
197 waterproof. Therefore, only a fire alarm system and fire extinguishers have been installed around
198 the castle, in addition to fireproof doors to prevent potential fires from spreading.

199 Considering the inability of the castle structure to prevent the risk of fire, on-site
200 countermeasures are deemed insufficient to protect the artefacts. Consequently, an
201 evacuation-based strategy is identified as the most appropriate approach to safeguard the
202 collections. This indicates that when a fire breaks out, objects would be retrieved and reallocated
203 outside the museum to a secure temporary storage facility. The MAN's risk mitigation process is
204 therefore centred on the prior preparation of an evacuation plan. As highlighted by ICCROM and
205 UNESCO (2016), a prerequisite for such a plan is the development of a comprehensive document
206 containing object information and spatial data to ensure a swift evacuation. Since the MAN lacks
207 a dedicated database to store and manage this information, this study proposes the design of a
208 dedicated evacuation database that meets the institution's DRM requirements and enables
209 evacuation personnel to execute object retrieval and relocation efficiently.

210 An important factor understood during the evacuation planning is that not all objects can be
211 removed within the time available, depending on how quickly a fire may spread. As such, the
212 development of a priority list of objects is recommended to ensure that artefacts considered most
213 significant are safeguarded first in emergencies (ICCROM & UNESCO, 2016). Each curator
214 responsible for a collection was therefore asked to compile a priority list of objects for inclusion in
215 the evacuation database. The criteria used to select objects for these priority lists varied amongst
216 curators, but generally involved a combination of factors such as historical or aesthetic
217 significance, accessibility, portability, and vulnerability.

218 *Evacuation Database*

219 Following the compilation of the list of objects, this study proceeded with the creation and
220 design of the database specifically for emergency usage, the first of its kind for the museum. The
221 diverse data collected was incorporated into a multi-faceted custom app in FileMaker Pro, a cross-
222 platform database software that allows users to create custom applications for managing,
223 organising, and sharing data. This software was chosen in part due to the lack of concrete
224 guidance from recommendations, except through the MAN's existing partnership with the Louvre
225 Museum, in which the same software is already being used for database purposes. The
226 configuration of the Filemaker Pro was designed in a manner that users with little knowledge in
227 computer or data science can easily grasp the fundamental knowledge to create, manage, retrieve,
228 and share databases, making this software ideal for the MAN, that is novice to data management.

229 The custom data app is intended to be play an active part during evacuations, as opposed to
230 being a mere passive database for storage backup. This meant that the data layout depicting the
231 priority objects must be easily read and understandable to swiftly evacuate the objects concerned
232 during disasters. For this reason, the data pertaining to each object to be inputted into the database
233 were determined via understanding what, where, and how the objects are, categories considered
234 most crucial for a successful evacuation. Physical properties include material, dimensions, and
235 weight, while non-physical fields include descriptive and documentation metadata, such as name,
236 identity number, location, and priority level. Photographs, maps, and pictograms are also included
237 to facilitate an easier understanding of the object and its location. The draft layout also includes a
238 blank section for editing of the status of the object, to indicate any special notes. The database

239 application was thus created and developed with the intent that it can be used throughout the DRM
 240 cycle of before, during, and after a disaster strikes (Figure 1). For security reasons, selected
 241 information pertaining to the object such as its inventory number is masked.
 242

243
 244 **Figure 1** – Sample page of a data layout depicting a one of the MAN’s chef-d’œuvre, of its properties,
 245 location, number of personnel needed to handle the object in word or image form for evacuation. The
 246 “statut” section allows additional notes to be taken.

247 One of the software’s features is that users can create an app that allows for the same dataset
 248 to be presented with targeted data layouts, such as highlighting certain data or hiding others
 249 depending on need. This, in turn, enables support for different phases of the DRM cycle, such as
 250 when one needs to preview the list of objects holistically (Figure 2). In this condensed layout, the
 251 dataset can also be sorted and filtered between categories. In doing so, it allows for strategic
 252 planning and analysis throughout the evacuation process, for the objects can be grouped by factors
 253 such as their location, type, or other fields, to develop and refine the optimal safeguarding actions
 254 and routes.
 255

Pré.	Niveau	Salle	Vitrine	Titre ou désignation	Número...	Poids	Long...	Largeur	Diam...	Epais...	Haüt...	Matériaux	Statut
1	N 01	2 (II)	5	objet en terre cuite	X000X		19,8 cm	7,7 cm			1,5 cm	terre cuite	
1	N 01	2 (II)	5	objet en terre cuite	X000X		85 cm				10 cm	or	
2	N 01	3 (III)	9	objet doré	X000X	2,5 kg					15 cm	céramique	
1	N 01	3 (III)	6	objet en céramique	X000X						9,3 cm	or	
2	N 01	3 (III)	8	objet doré	X000X	83 g				11 cm	11 cm	or	
2	N 01	3 (III)	8	objet doré	X000X	321,1 g	82,5 cm					alliage cuivreux	en prêt
1	N 01	3 (III)	1	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	2,8 kg					480 cm	alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	3 (III)	9	objet doré	X000X	509 g	15,8 cm					or	
1	N 01	3 (III)	9	objet doré	X000X	229 g	78 cm					or	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	16	objet en bronze	X000X	500 g				20 cm		bronze	
2	N 01	4 (IV)	16	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X							alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	16	objet en céramique	X000X	500 g				12 cm	12 cm	céramique	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	16	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	5 kg				22 cm	39 cm	alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	16	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	10 g						alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	1	objet en céramique	X000X	800 g				30 cm	20 cm	céramique	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	1	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X					13 cm	5,5 cm	alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	13	objet doré	X000X	229 g				26 cm	8,4 cm	or	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	13	objet doré	X000X	55 g				13 cm		or	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	13	objet doré	X000X	99 g				20 cm		or	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	13	objet doré	X000X	24,7 g				5 cm		or	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	13	objet doré	X000X	83 g	20 cm					or	
2	N 01	4 (IV)	12	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X					13 cm		alliage cuivreux	déplacé temporairement dans la salle photo
1	N 01	4 (IV)	12	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	50 cm						alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	12	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	2,4 kg	51,5 cm					alliage cuivreux	déplacé temporairement dans la salle photo
1	N 01	4 (IV)	12	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	50 cm						alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	12	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	50 cm						alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	12	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	50 cm						alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	14	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	39,5 cm				38,5 cm		alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	14	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	19,5 cm	5,5 cm					alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	14	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	19,5 cm	5,5 cm					alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	14	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	10 cm	2 cm					alliage cuivreux	
1	N 01	4 (IV)	14	objet en alliage de cuivre	X000X	12 cm	2 cm					alliage cuivreux	

256
 257 **Figure 2** – Sample page of a condensed data layout depicting the overview of all priority objects, sorted
 258 by room order. The names and inventory number are masked for security reasons.

259 The individual and overview data layouts are interlinked and directly editable, meaning one
260 field that is edited will directly be reflected in the other layout, reducing redundancy. Moreover, the
261 application also functions on mobile operating systems, thereby increasing its accessibility and
262 allows for the possibility of real-time digital recording via a tablet system during the evacuation
263 process. The software further provides options for users to host their custom applications on-
264 premises or in the software's own cloud, and provides the ability to share the app across local
265 networks, via the cloud drive, using the peer-to-peer function, or exported for printing.

266 In summary, the custom database app and its features not only provide a safe digital platform
267 for to store, manage, and share the museum's object data prior to disaster scenarios, it is also
268 directly usable for locating objects and instant record keeping during the evacuation process as
269 well. This one-stop custom app centralises all object information stored before and during
270 disasters, to act as the reference point to enable the recovery process after disasters, and
271 decreases the likelihood of the mismanagement and the loss of data.

272 *Revised Evacuation Database*

273 The custom app created through this study was discussed iteratively through meetings with all
274 personnel related to the DRM of the MAN, both internal management and external parties. In
275 particular, the comments of the local fire services were especially important, for the firemen
276 oversee the actual evacuation process due to their expertise in fire hazards. They determined that
277 the database draft presented, though precise, lacked other information that could facilitate a more
278 efficient evacuation. This is because the firemen may not have the necessary knowledge of the
279 museum, its objects, or heritage conservation to fully comprehend the scope of the DRM process.
280 As such, this database, intended to be a one-stop app for the entire evacuation process, should
281 provide greater detail on the MAN in order to enable external personnel to quickly understand the
282 knowledge needed to safeguard the museum's objects.

283 After further consulting the international guidelines, any successful safeguarding plan requires
284 the personnel to not only understand the objects, but also the spaces holistically and individually
285 (ICCROM & UNESCO, 2016). Consequently, several other datasets, in addition to dedicated data
286 layouts, have been added to the database. As an example, an additional layout depicting a section
287 of the museum at-a-glance has been added (Figure 3). This layout provides clarity to evacuation
288 personnel by illustrating the approximate locations of all objects needed for evacuation within a
289 given room on a given floor, with the approximate location indicated on a map. Each bubble
290 indicating an object's location is clickable and redirects the user to the corresponding data layout
291 detailing the object. In doing so, firemen can understand the museum's spaces and locations at
292 large, to plan to evacuate multiple nearby objects in one attempt. This corrects an aspect that was
293 not considered previously, to provide an overview of multiple objects in relation to the spaces.
294

295

296 **Figure 3** – Data layout depicting the approximate locations of priority objects within a given area of the
297 MAN. The priority level for the objects is colour-coded for easier grouping.

298 The layout for each object was also updated to include additional features (Figure 4), such as
 299 buttons to redirect users back to the at-a-glance view of the museum. An additional field to assign
 300 a unique identifier to an object during evacuation is also added. As recommended by ICCROM
 301 and UNESCO (2016), this ensures the object and its reallocation is tracked, documented, and
 302 retrievable in the aftermath of a disaster. Since the MAN has not formulated a numbering system,
 303 this study proposes an identifier that encodes an object's original location, the order in which it was
 304 evacuated, and the team that performed the action. For example, the identifier MAN.E.S7.V3.1(01)
 305 indicates that the object is from the MAN, on the Entresol level [E], in room 7 [S7], inside showcase
 306 X [VX], and that it was the first object retrieved [1], with the suffix (01) denoting the initials of the
 307 evacuation team. This structure is intended to ensure that each evacuation is clearly
 308 understandable, and to allow for post-disaster evaluation of the DRM strategy.
 309

310
 311 **Figure 4** – Revised data layout for each object with additional functions and explanations added to
 312 enhance its usability.

313 Other datasets have also been added to the database in an effort to increase the
 314 comprehensiveness of the custom app. Contact information of all relevant personnel, locations of
 315 on-site fire safety equipment, additional pages to input in detail any incidents during the evacuation,
 316 and a glossary to explain the information presented in this app have been added to the database
 317 app to increase its functionality beyond detailing object information. The software supports this via
 318 the modifiable ontological model that allows datasets to be interlinked, ensuring the accessibility
 319 of the app and ease for retrieving the corresponding data between the multiple layouts (Figure 5).
 320

321

322 **Figure 5** – The ontological model defines relationships between the datasets, linked via common keys
 323 between data fields, enabling the same data to be simultaneously edited and presented across layouts.

324 Not only did the result of this revised database enabled the fire services to gain a more in-depth
 325 understanding of the MAN, the museum’s own curators were also able to benefit from the app to
 326 gain a more holistic understanding of the priority objects and their conditions under the DRM plan.
 327 The museum map depicted within the database app enabled curators to realise that certain objects
 328 designated for evacuation are placed at a distance to fire exits, meaning a longer time is needed
 329 to evacuate those objects. For this reason, objects have been reallocated to locations closer to fire
 330 exits, especially those in the archives or storage rooms, so that they are prepared well in advance
 331 of any potential disaster scenarios. This decreases the time needed to retrieve them and increases
 332 the chances of a successful evacuation.

333 As for objects already on exhibition, reallocation is limited by the number of available
 334 showcases and the potential disruption to the museum’s archaeological narrative. Additionally,
 335 several objects may be currently located in the same room but encased in different showcases,
 336 which creates an unnecessary burden for the firemen tasked with opening them. Nonetheless, the
 337 evacuation database enables the curators to factor these into account in deciding the new
 338 placement of objects, as the MAN is currently undergoing major renovations that include the
 339 complete alteration of exhibition rooms. This effectively embeds DRM planning into the museum’s
 340 ongoing renovation masterplan, ensuring that future displays are arranged to facilitate, rather than
 341 hinder, the swift evacuation of artefacts.

342 Discussion

343 Through the application of DRM guidelines developed by cultural organisations, this study was
 344 able to identify the primary risk of fire, which endangers the MAN’s collections. The subsequent
 345 risk mitigation efforts, in the form of an evacuation database, transformed the museum’s
 346 operational response to fire hazards in several ways. Firstly, the revised app with additional data
 347 layouts and mapping features bridges the previously identified knowledge gap between
 348 conservation staff and emergency responders, such as providing the firemen with multimodal
 349 views of the museum. Secondly, the database analysis acted as a diagnostic tool for spatial
 350 management. By visualising the distance between priority objects and fire exits, curators were able
 351 to identify and rectify storage areas, resulting in the reallocation of priority objects to more
 352 accessible zones. Finally, the iterative design process, informed by direct feedback from
 353 stakeholders, demonstrated that the database is not a mere static digital record, but an active
 354 decision support system.

355 Thus, this study demonstrates that a dedicated, visual database can serve as a key element in
 356 mitigating disaster risks in museums, which is consistent with the recommendations of cultural
 357 organisations on the importance of adequate documentation in DRM (ICCROM & UNESCO, 2016;
 358 UNESCO, 2010). By enabling the visualisation of museum spaces and objects in relation to

359 safeguard requirements, the database developed through this study allowed DRM strategies to be
360 incorporated into the operational structure of the MAN to increase its resilience against future
361 disasters, which can provide a positive reference point for other museums in establishing DRM
362 strategies.

363 Nonetheless, it is crucial to devise a database not as a standalone project, but in coordination
364 with other elements of the overall DRM strategy to achieve best results (ICCROM & UNESCO,
365 2016; Wegener, 2024). Thus, drills putting this database app to use should be tested to ensure its
366 functionality during emergencies. In addition, capacity building workshops and frequent meetings
367 between the MAN and the fire services are recommended on a regular basis, to ensure the relevant
368 knowledge on conservation and fire safety are transferred between both sides.

369 Another factor is that the DRM should not be a static protocol once it has been developed.
370 Renovations, temporary reallocations, and other modifications of both short and long term periods
371 can decrease the efficiency of the safeguarding plan, which contributes to the risk of disassociation
372 if left outdated. Threats by other risks could also increase in time. Considering the MAN's
373 renovation and modification works will continue throughout the decade, adequate changes to an
374 object's status and location should be reflected in the database in a timely manner, and additional risk
375 assessments or DRM strategies may need to be conducted to counter new risks.

376 Finally, considering the changes in the role of museums in society over the past decade, it is
377 noted that museums should constantly engage with the public to provide greater transparency and
378 learning (Díaz-Andreu, 2017). Currently, the curators at the MAN have noticed public apathy
379 towards the museum and its work (MAN, 2017, 2023). The DRM project can therefore serve as a
380 gateway to connect with local communities in enhancing their understanding of the museum, such
381 as via enlisting volunteers in drills to simulate the evacuation process of both visitors and objects,
382 providing a more comprehensive understanding of the DRM plan in action.

383 **Conclusion**

384 This research demonstrates that bridging the gap between theoretical DRM frameworks
385 developed by international cultural organisations and the practical realities of cultural institutions
386 is both feasible and essential. Having assessed that the primary risk the Musée d'Archéologie
387 Nationale faces is fire, this study highlights that the preparedness phase of DRM strategies can be
388 consolidated through developing a dedicated database. By creating a custom app with an
389 ontological model defining the relationship between datasets, this research provides a critical
390 interface between heritage safeguarding and emergency response planning. This database
391 supports all phases of the DRM cycle: before disasters, it enables strategic planning via integrating
392 object information, spatial data, and emergency response plans; during disasters, targeted layouts
393 provide immediate access to evacuation orders, procedures, and relevant contacts; and after
394 disasters, the recorded data aids recovery and evaluation, allowing for critical analysis.

395 The results at the Musée d'Archéologie Nationale show that a dedicated evacuation database
396 contributes to a more robust long-term heritage conservation strategy, by improving the ability to
397 safeguard movable heritage within Disaster Risk Management planning. The lessons learnt
398 through developing this database can serve as a reference point for other museums' emergency
399 planning, providing a framework that can be adapted to the diverse operational needs of different
400 institutions. Continuous development of a dedicated emergency database will help cultural
401 institutions housing movable heritage become more disaster resilient in the face of challenging
402 risks, supporting the global imperative to better protect humanity's heritage.

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417 Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

418 The data, scripts, code, and supplementary information used in this study are subject to
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